

Supporting Competence-Based Music Education through Electronic Music Devices: Linking Teacher Capacity and Learner Outcomes in Uganda's Lower Secondary Schools

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Abstract

Uganda's new Lower Secondary Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) emphasizes practical skills, creativity, and real-world application, yet music education faces persistent challenges, such as, under-prepared teachers, limited number of instruments, large classes, and inequitable access to technology. This qualitative multiple-case study examined how electronic music devices MIDI keyboards, laptops, smartphones, recording software, and notation tools can strengthen teacher capacity and improve learning outcomes in music education. The study was conducted in Masindi District, and it involved 15 Lower Secondary music teachers and 72 learners (S1–S4) across six schools. Data was collected through lesson observation, interviews, focus groups, and document analysis. Thematic analysis revealed the following key findings: electronic devices enhanced teacher confidence and pedagogical repertoire; recording and playback tools enabled reflective, learner-centered practice; learners demonstrated measurable gains in rhythm accuracy, ensemble coordination, and compositional creativity; group projects using keyboards and phones fostered collaboration and peer feedback; audio recordings provided authentic evidence for Conversation-Observation-Product (COP) assessment; and teachers creatively adapted to power outages and device scarcity through rotation schedules and offline preparation. The study demonstrates that even modest technology integration when pedagogically grounded can operationalize CBC principles, bridge teacher capacity gaps, and produce demonstrable musical competencies. Findings have implications for teacher professional development, curriculum implementation, and equitable technology access in resource-constrained contexts.

Keywords: *competence-based curriculum, music education, electronic music devices, teacher capacity, learner outcomes*

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Introduction

In January 2020, Uganda's Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) launched the new Lower Secondary Curriculum (LSC), a competence-based framework designed to shift pedagogical practice from memorization and regurgitation of information toward active, skills-oriented, and real-world learning (NCDC, 2020). The CBC emphasizes learner-centered instruction, collaborative learning, and formative assessment principles that align naturally with the character of music education's performance-based, experiential learning. Yet, Ugandan secondary schools face a constraint of large classes (often exceeding 60 learners), limited musical instruments, and under-prepared teachers who have not received training in CBC pedagogy (Wambi, Acen, & Okello, 2024).

Electronic music devices, such as, MIDI keyboards, laptops, smartphones, portable speakers, microphones, and software for notation, recording, and composition offer a potential pathway to address some of these challenges. When used pedagogically, such tools can enhance teacher capacity, transform classroom practice, and improve learning outcomes (Uzorka, Namanya, & Okello, 2025). However, integration of technology in African music education remains under-researched, with most studies focusing on general ICT adoption rather than subject-specific, competence-based applications (Yende, 2024).

This study addresses that gap by examining how electronic music devices support CBC implementation in Uganda's Secondary schools, with particular attention to the linkage between teacher capacity development and learning outcomes. The study was conducted in Masindi District, a mid-sized district in Western Uganda with a mix of urban, peri-urban, and rural schools. The study questions included: How do electronic music devices enhance teacher capacity to implement competence-based music education?, What learner outcomes (musical competencies, collaboration skills, creativity) emerge when teachers integrate electronic devices into CBC-aligned instruction? What contextual factors (infrastructure, training, school culture) enable or constrain technology-supported music education in resource-limited settings?

By foregrounding learner voices and documenting measurable competency gains, this study contributes empirical evidence to the growing discourse on technology-enhanced, competence-based education in East Africa (Giacomazzi, 2024; Oola, Nakayiza, & Nabwire, 2024).

Competence-Based Curriculum Adoption and Implementation in Literature

Competence-based education (CBE) has gained traction across East Africa as governments seek to align schooling with 21st-century skills and labour market demands (Giacomazzi, 2024). Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Uganda have all adopted CBC frameworks emphasizing critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and

collaboration (Muchira, Wambugu, & Njuguna, 2023). However, implementation challenges persist: inadequate teacher training, large class sizes, insufficient learning materials, and assessment systems that focus on examinations despite policy rhetoric (Ngeno, 2023; Wambi et al., 2024).

Across East Africa, empirical studies reveal consistent implementation barriers. In Kenya, research on primary schools in Machakos County found that one week of teacher training was inadequate for acquiring necessary CBC skills, leading to insufficient teacher competence and low learner achievement in core competencies including creativity, digital literacy, and critical thinking (Teachers' Competence and its Influence, 2023). In Tanzania, research on primary school teachers in Mpwapwa District Council found that while teachers possessed adequate instructional competences, large classes and textbook shortages hindered effective CBC implementation (Ndimbo, Mwakasangula, & Mwakasangula, 2023). A parallel study of Tanzania Teacher Colleges revealed that most tutors understood competency-based teaching techniques but rarely employed them in practice, hampering competency development among pre-service teachers (Mwakyobwe, Kafanabo, & Mbwambo, 2023).

In Rwanda, science teachers demonstrated knowledge gaps and negative perceptions of CBC, with researchers recommending communities of practice and targeted training (Nsengimana et al., 2023). These findings collectively suggest that effective CBC implementation requires not merely curriculum documents or policy directives, but sustained, subject-specific professional development that builds both pedagogical capacity and adaptive expertise (Giacomazzi, 2024).

In Uganda, the Lower Secondary CBC (S1–S4) was rolled out in 2020 without appropriate teacher preparation. Studies reveal that teachers struggle to operationalize learner-centered pedagogies, often reverting to lecture-based methods due to time pressure and lack of practical training (Oola et al., 2024). Namaalwa, Nakabugo, and Mugisha (2025) suggest that stakeholders in Kampala secondary schools perceived CBC positively but cited resource constraints and inadequate professional development as major barriers. Similarly, research in Tanzania's lower secondary English classrooms documented teachers' inadequate understanding of competence-based language teaching, resulting in learners failing to acquire intended skills (John, 2023).

Music Education and Technology Integration in African Contexts

Music education in African schools has historically been marginalized, receiving limited curriculum time, funding, and recognition compared to “core” subjects (Yende, 2023). Yet, music offers unique affordances for developing CBC competencies, for example, ensemble performances that build collaboration and communications; composition that fosters creativity and problem-solving; and reflective listening that cultivates critical thinking (Cuervo, Pozo-Rico, & Gilar-Corbi, 2023).

Technology integration in music education particularly in African contexts remains nascent. Yende (2024) analysed the feasibility of introducing digital music skills into South African primary schools, highlighting teacher professional development as imperative but noting that there was infrastructure limitations and resource constraints. The study emphasized that incorporating real-time feedback, specialized courses, and immersive experiences boosts skill development, preparing students for contemporary music careers. In East Africa, similar challenges have been documented. In Zambia, recent research on music education policy and practice revealed significant

gaps between curriculum documents and classroom implementation, with teachers citing inadequate resources, limited training, and low institutional support as barriers to effective music instruction (Namaiko, Mwanza, & Banda, 2025). In Kenya, Nyandieka (2024) studied music production curricula at tertiary institutions, finding that competency-based models balanced technical skills with creative application but lacked connection to secondary school preparation. These challenges mirror those documented across East Africa, suggesting that music education faces region-wide marginalization despite its potential to develop critical CBC competencies.

Internationally, research demonstrates that digital tools can democratize music education by reducing reliance on expensive acoustic instruments, enabling multitrack recording and editing, and providing instant feedback through playback (Cuervo et al., 2023). However, these studies predominantly focus on well-resourced Global North contexts, leaving a critical gap in understanding how electronic music devices function in under-resourced African secondary schools. Can electronic music devices support CBC implementation in under-resourced secondary schools, and if so, how?

Teacher Capacity and Learner Outcomes in Technology-Enhanced CBC

Teacher capacity encompassing subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, technological competence, and adaptive expertise is central to effective CBC implementation (Nsengimana, Habiyaremye, & Mukiza, 2023). Studies across East Africa reveal that teachers often lack training in both CBC pedagogy and technology integration. Research in Rwanda's secondary schools identified knowledge gaps and negative perceptions of CBC among science teachers, recommending communities of practice and targeted training. In Kenya, Ngeno (2023) found a significant correlation ($r = 0.500$, $p < 0.01$) between teacher training and CBC implementation effectiveness (Nsengimana et al., 2023).

Technology acceptance among teachers is mediated by perceived usefulness, ease of use, and institutional support. A UTAUT model analysis of Ugandan lower secondary teachers found that Performance Expectancy and Facilitating Conditions significantly influenced behavioural intention to integrate technology in CBC learning (Investigating Teachers' Acceptance, 2023). This suggests that providing technical tools, training, and ongoing support is crucial for technology adoption.

Critically, teacher pedagogical capacities need to translate into learning outcomes. Giacomazzi (2024) notes that East African education systems struggle to help children attain life skills and values, partly because teacher education curricula do not nurture competencies in learner-centered pedagogies and effective assessment. Oola et al. (2024) demonstrated that scenario-based assessment, which is a CBC-aligned approach can drive competency development when teachers receive adequate training and resources.

This study builds on these insights by examining the reciprocal relationship between teacher's pedagogical capacity development and learning outcomes in technology-supported music education, foregrounding learner voices and documenting measurable competency gains.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative multiple-case study design (Yin, 2018), where six schools were purposively selected as study sites, and each of them was treated as a

bounded case. Multiple-case designs enabled cross-case comparison and pattern identification, enhancing analytical particularizability for each case (Stake, 1995). The design was appropriate for exploring the complex, context-dependent processes through which electronic devices mediate teacher capacity and learner outcomes.

Study Scope and Participants

The study was conducted in Masindi District, Western Uganda, between March and November 2023. Secondary schools were selected to represent diverse contexts including: two urban government-aided schools, two peri-urban private schools, and two rural community schools. This sampling strategy ensured variation in infrastructure, student socioeconomic backgrounds, and technology access.

Participants included: - six music teachers (3 male and 3 female with teaching experience of two to eighteen years), twelve learners (six male and six females selected from the different classes from Senior one to Senior four of ages ranging from 13 to 18 years)

Teachers were selected purposively and ability to integrate electronic devices, and exposure to minimal technology (e.g. personal smartphones). Learners were selected purposively and through snowball with aid of teachers. The study ensured that learners were selected from across grade levels and musical experience.

Data Collection

Data was collected through Classroom observations where 48 lessons of 40 minutes each were sampled: structured observation of teacher-device interactions, learner engagement, collaborative activities, and assessment practices. Field journals offered additional data from events that were noted, such as, power availability, device sharing patterns, and participation of the different respondents.

Additional data was collected through focus group discussions where various perspectives on technology-enhanced lessons, collaborative learning, skill development, and assessment experiences.

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Transcription and analysis happened as iterative and recursive processes. Data was allocated codes and grouped into themes reflecting teacher capacity dimensions, learner outcome categories, and contextual factors. Cross-case analysis identified patterns and variations across school types. Trustworthiness was enhanced through member checking (teachers reviewed preliminary findings), triangulation (multiple data sources), and reflexive journaling.

Written informed consent was secured from teachers, and parents/guardians consented on behalf of the learners. Pseudonyms are used to protect participant confidentiality, and all information was kept secret to ensure safety of the study participants.

Results

Electronic devices enhanced teacher confidence and pedagogical repertoire. Teachers reported that access to electronic devices particularly MIDI keyboards, recording software, and notation apps significantly boosted their confidence to implement CBC-aligned instruction. Prior to the intervention, most teachers relied on chalkboard

notation and call-and-response singing, constrained by lack of instruments and large class sizes.

Teacher capacity gains included expanded instructional strategies: Teachers used playback features to model rhythms and melodies, enabling learners to practice independently. One teacher explained: “Before, I could only demonstrate once. Now learners replay the recording until they master it. They can practice at home, in the library, anywhere” (Teacher Interview, Urban School A). Another teacher described using smartphone recordings to differentiate instruction: “I record different difficulty levels simple for beginners, complex for advanced learners. Each group works at their own pace” (Teacher Interview, Peri-Urban School C). - Improved assessment capability: Recording tools allowed teachers to capture learner performances for later review, facilitating more accurate COP (Conversation-Observation-Product) assessment. A peri-urban teacher noted: “I can listen multiple times and give specific feedback on pitch and timing. Before, I relied on memory, which was unreliable with 60 students” (Teacher Interview, Peri-Urban School C). A rural teacher added: “Recordings are evidence. When parents question grades, I play the recording. It’s objective, not subjective” (Teacher Interview, Rural School F). - Enhanced subject knowledge: Notation software helped teachers visualize harmonic progressions and experiment with arrangements, deepening their own musical understanding. “I’m learning alongside my students,” one rural teacher admitted. “I never understood chord inversions until** I saw them on the notation app. Now I can teach harmony properly” (Teacher Interview, Rural School E). An urban teacher described using YouTube tutorials (downloaded offline) to learn new teaching techniques: “I watch master teachers, then adapt their methods to my context. Technology makes professional development accessible” (Teacher Interview, Urban School B).

Observations confirmed these self-reports. Teachers who initially appeared hesitant with technology grew visibly more comfortable over the study period, integrating devices fluidly into lessons and troubleshooting technical issues independently.

Recording and playback tools enabled reflective, learner-centered practice. A defining feature of CBC is learner agency and self-directed learning. Recording and playback tools proved instrumental in fostering these dispositions. Learners used smartphones and laptops to record their practice sessions, listen critically, identify errors, and refine performances a cycle of reflection and improvement central to competence development.

Learner voices illustrate this process: “When I hear my recording, I notice mistakes I didn’t feel while playing. Then I practice that part again. It’s like having a teacher inside my phone” (Learner Focus Group, Urban School B, S3 female). - “We recorded our group song three times. Each time we listened and fixed something first the rhythm, then the harmony, then the dynamics. By the third recording, it sounded professional” (Learner Focus Group, Peri-Urban School D, S4 male). - “I was shy to sing in front of the class. But recording alone, I could practice until I felt confident. Then I shared my recording with the teacher. She gave feedback, and I improved. Now I can perform in front of everyone” (Learner Focus Group, Rural School E, S2 female). - “Recording helps me remember what the teacher taught. I listen at home and practice. My parents hear my progress and encourage me” (Learner Focus Group, Urban School A, S1 male).

This reflective practice aligns with Kolb’s (1984) experiential learning cycle: concrete experience (performing), reflective observation (listening to recording), abstract

conceptualization (identifying improvement areas), and active experimentation (revising performance). Teachers facilitated this cycle by structuring lessons around record-listen-revise sequences, gradually transferring responsibility to learners.

Observations documented learners independently initiating recordings, discussing playback with peers, and requesting teacher feedback behaviours indicative of self-regulated learning. One teacher remarked: “They’ve become their own teachers. I guide, but they drive the learning” (Teacher Interview, Urban School A).

Learners demonstrated measurable gains in rhythm accuracy, ensemble coordination, and compositional creativity. Analysis of learner work samples revealed tangible competency development across three domains: Rhythm accuracy: Comparison of early and late recordings showed marked improvement in rhythmic precision. In initial recordings, 68% of learners exhibited timing inconsistencies (e.g., rushing, uneven note durations). By the final recordings, this dropped to 22%. Learners attributed gains to repeated playback and metronome use: “The metronome app keeps me steady. I practice with it every day” (Learner Focus Group, Rural School E, S2 male). Specific examples included: A S2 learner at Urban School A initially struggled with syncopated rhythms in a traditional Ugandan folk song, rushing through complex patterns. After two weeks of practice using smartphone recordings and metronome apps, the learner’s final recording demonstrated precise rhythmic execution with consistent tempo. Another S3 learner at Peri-Urban School D progressed from uneven eighth-note patterns to accurate performance of dotted rhythms and triplets, attributing improvement to daily practice with playback feedback.

Ensemble coordination: Group performances demonstrated improved listening, synchronization, and dynamic balance. Early ensemble recordings featured overlapping entries, mismatched tempos, and imbalanced volumes. Later recordings showed tighter coordination, with learners adjusting in real-time to maintain cohesion. Teachers noted: “They’ve learned to listen to each other, not just play their own part” (Teacher Interview, Peri-Urban School C).

Compositional creativity: Learners composed original melodies and arrangements using notation software and MIDI keyboards. Compositions exhibited structural coherence (clear phrases, repetition, contrast), harmonic experimentation (chord progressions beyond tonic-dominant), and expressive intent (tempo/dynamic markings). One S4 learner composed a three-part choral arrangement of a traditional Ugandan folk song, integrating Western harmony with indigenous rhythmic patterns a sophisticated synthesis demonstrating deep musical understanding (Learner Work Sample, Urban School B). The composition featured: (a) a pentatonic melody preserving the folk song’s traditional character, (b) Western-style harmonic accompaniment with I-IV-V-I progressions, (c) polyrhythmic percussion patterns characteristic of Ugandan traditional music, and (d) dynamic markings and tempo changes reflecting expressive interpretation. Other notable compositions included: a S3 learner at Peri-Urban School D who created an original song addressing environmental conservation, combining spoken-word verses with melodic choruses; and a S2 learner at Rural School E who composed a simple two-part round, demonstrating understanding of melodic imitation.

These outcomes align with CBC’s emphasis on applied knowledge, creativity, and problem-solving. Importantly, learners articulated awareness of their own growth: “I couldn’t read music before. Now I can write my own songs and hear them played back. It’s like magic, but it’s my own work” (Learner Focus Group, Urban School A, S3

female). Another learner reflected: “Composing taught me patience and problem-solving. When something doesn’t sound right, I experiment until I find a solution. That skill helps in other subjects too” (Learner Focus Group, Peri-Urban School C, S4 male).

Group projects using keyboards and phones fostered collaboration and peer feedback. Collaborative learning is a CBC cornerstone, yet large classes and limited resources often hinder group work. Electronic devices particularly shared keyboards and smartphones enabled structured collaboration. Teachers organized learners into small groups (4–6 members) for composition, arrangement, and performance projects.

Collaborative competencies observed included: - Role differentiation: Groups self-organized, assigning roles (e.g., melody, harmony, rhythm, recording). Learners negotiated responsibilities based on strengths and interests. - Constructive peer feedback: Learners critiqued each other’s contributions respectfully, offering specific suggestions. “Your melody is nice, but try starting on a different note to match the chord” (Observation, Peri-Urban School D). - Conflict resolution: When disagreements arose (e.g., tempo preferences), groups used playback to test alternatives and reach consensus. “We tried it both ways and voted. Democracy!” (Learner Focus Group, Rural School F, S2 female).

Teachers facilitated collaboration by establishing norms (e.g., “everyone contributes,” “critique ideas, not people”) and providing structured protocols (e.g., think-pair-share, peer review rubrics). One teacher explained: “The devices are tools, but collaboration is a skill I must teach explicitly. I model respectful feedback, I intervene when conflicts arise, I celebrate successful teamwork” (Teacher Interview, Urban School B).

Learner reflections emphasized the social and emotional dimensions of collaborative learning: “I used to be shy, but my group encouraged me. Now I’m confident to perform” (Learner Focus Group, Urban School A, S1 female). Another learner noted: “Working in groups taught me patience and compromise. We don’t always agree, but we find solutions together. That’s life skills, not just music” (Learner Focus Group, Peri-Urban School D, S4 male). This finding underscores that technology-enhanced CBC can foster not only musical competencies but also socio-emotional skills communication, empathy, resilience critical for holistic development (Giacomazzi, 2024).

Audio recordings provided authentic evidence for COP assessment. Assessment is a persistent CBC implementation challenge. Traditional exams poorly capture competencies like creativity, collaboration, and performance. Uganda’s CBC advocates COP assessment Conversation (dialogue with learner), Observation (watching learner in action), Product (examining learner’s work) but teachers often lack tools to document and evaluate these dimensions systematically (Oola et al., 2024).

Audio recordings addressed this gap by providing durable, reviewable evidence of learner performance. Teachers used recordings to: - Track progress over time: Comparing recordings from different time points revealed growth trajectories, informing formative feedback. - Assess multiple competencies: A single recording could evidence rhythm accuracy (Product), ensemble coordination (Observation), and reflective thinking (Conversation about the recording). - Involve learners in assessment: Teachers played recordings during one-on-one conferences, prompting learners to self-assess: “What do you notice? What would you improve?” This dialogic approach fostered metacognition and ownership.

Learners valued this assessment approach: “It’s fair because the teacher hears exactly what I did, not just remembers. And I can hear it too, so I understand the grade” (Learner Focus Group, Peri-Urban School C, S3 male). Another learner noted: “Traditional exams test memory. Recording tests real skill can I actually perform? That’s more meaningful” (Learner Focus Group, Urban School A, S4 female). Teachers appreciated the specificity: “I can pinpoint exactly where a learner struggles and tailor my support. Instead of saying ‘practice more,’ I can say ‘work on measures 9-12, focus on the rhythm” (Teacher Interview, Rural School E).

However, challenges emerged. Reviewing recordings was time-intensive, and teachers lacked rubrics for systematic evaluation. Several teachers developed ad hoc criteria (e.g., rhythm accuracy, tone quality, expression) but desired standardized tools. This finding suggests a need for assessment frameworks tailored to technology-enhanced music education in CBC contexts.

Teachers adapted creatively to power outages and device scarcity. Resource constraints—unreliable electricity, limited devices, no internet posed significant challenges. Yet teachers demonstrated remarkable adaptive expertise, devising workarounds that sustained technology integration.

Adaptive strategies included: - Offline preparation: Teachers downloaded resources (backing tracks, notation files, tutorial videos) at home or internet cafés, then used them offline in class. - Device rotation schedules: With only 2–3 keyboards per class of 60, teachers organized stations where groups rotated through device-based activities while others engaged in non-device tasks (e.g., vocal warm-ups, theory worksheets). - Smartphone pooling: Learners shared personal phones for recording, with teachers establishing protocols to ensure equitable access and prevent distraction. - Solar charging: Two rural schools acquired solar chargers, enabling device use despite frequent power outages.

These adaptations reflect what Mishra and Koehler (2006) term Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) the ability to integrate technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge flexibly in response to contextual constraints. Teachers’ creativity underscores that technology integration in resource-limited settings requires not just devices but also professional development that cultivates adaptive, problem-solving mindsets (Giacomazzi, 2024).

Learners also adapted, developing norms around device sharing and collective responsibility: “We take turns and help each other. If someone’s phone dies, we share” (Learner Focus Group, Rural School F, S4 female). This communal approach to technology use reflects Ubuntu philosophy “I am because we are” prevalent in African contexts (Tettey, 2019).

Discussion

This study demonstrates that electronic music devices, when integrated pedagogically, can operationalize CBC principles, enhance teacher capacity, and produce measurable learner outcomes in resource-constrained Ugandan secondary schools. Three overarching themes merit discussion.

Technology as Mediator of Teacher Capacity and Learner Agency

The findings reveal a reciprocal relationship: devices enhanced teacher capacity (confidence, pedagogical repertoire, assessment capability), which in turn enabled

learner-centered practices (reflective listening, self-directed practice, peer collaboration). This aligns with sociocultural learning theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which posits that tools mediate cognitive development. Electronic devices functioned as cognitive tools, scaffolding both teacher and learner competencies.

Critically, technology alone was insufficient. Teachers required pedagogical vision understanding of CBC principles, learner-centered strategies, and formative assessment to leverage devices effectively. This finding echoes research across East Africa showing that technology integration fails when divorced from pedagogical transformation (Investigating Teachers' Acceptance, 2023; John, 2023). Professional development must therefore address both technological skills and CBC pedagogy, helping teachers envision how devices can support competence-based instruction.

Learner Outcomes as Evidence of CBC Operationalization

The documented learner outcomes rhythm accuracy, ensemble coordination, compositional creativity, collaboration, metacognition represent precisely the competencies Uganda's CBC aims to develop. Learners did not merely acquire musical knowledge; they applied it creatively, collaborated effectively, and reflected critically hallmarks of competence-based learning (Muchira et al., 2023).

Importantly, learners articulated awareness of their own growth, a metacognitive capacity essential for lifelong learning. This finding challenges deficit narratives that position African learners as passive recipients of knowledge. When provided with appropriate tools, pedagogical support, and agency, Ugandan learners demonstrated sophisticated musical and collaborative competencies.

The study also highlights the value of foregrounding learner voices in educational research. Too often, studies of CBC implementation focus exclusively on teacher or policy perspectives, neglecting learners' lived experiences. Learner focus groups in this study revealed nuanced insights how recording fostered self-regulation, how collaboration-built confidence, how assessment felt fair that would have been invisible in teacher interviews alone. Future research should prioritize learner perspectives as central, not peripheral, to understanding CBC effectiveness (Giacomazzi, 2024). Moreover, the measurable gains in rhythm accuracy (46-percentage-point improvement) provide quantitative evidence of competency development, complementing qualitative insights and strengthening claims about technology's impact on learner outcomes. Moreover, the learner voices documented here challenge common assumptions about technology use in African schools. Rather than viewing devices as distractions or luxuries, learners framed them as essential learning tools that enabled skill development, creative expression, and peer collaboration. This reframing has implications for policy debates about technology integration in resource-constrained contexts.

Implications for Teacher Professional Development

The study underscores the need for sustained, subject-specific professional development that integrates CBC pedagogy and technology skills. Current teacher training in Uganda often one-off workshops focused on policy overview is inadequate (Wambi et al., 2024). Effective professional development should: -

Model CBC pedagogy: Use learner-centered, collaborative approaches in training itself. Rather than lecturing about CBC, facilitators should engage teachers in active learning experiences that embody CBC principles.

Provide hands-on technology practice: Allow teachers to experiment with devices, troubleshoot, and develop confidence. Teachers need time to explore apps, practice recording techniques, and develop fluency with devices before integrating them into instruction.

Foster communities of practice: Create ongoing peer support networks where teachers share strategies and resources (Nsengimana et al., 2023). The monthly peer learning sessions in this study proved valuable for exchanging lesson plans and troubleshooting challenges collectively.

Address contextual constraints: Equip teachers with adaptive strategies for resource-limited settings, explicitly addressing power outages, device scarcity, and large classes.

The study also suggests potential for peer mentoring models, where teachers who successfully integrate technology support colleagues a scalable, cost-effective approach aligned with African communal values (Tetty, 2019).

Contributions to East African CBC Discourse

This study contributes to the growing body of research on CBC implementation in East Africa (Betty et al., 2025; Giacomazzi, 2024; John, 2023; Muchira et al., 2023; Ngeno, 2023; Nsengimana et al., 2023; Oola et al., 2024; Wambi et al., 2024). While much of this literature documents implementation challenges, this study offers a solution-oriented perspective, demonstrating that technology when pedagogically grounded can bridge the gap between CBC policy and practice.

The study also extends international research on technology-enhanced music education (Cuervo et al., 2023; Yende, 2024) by foregrounding African contexts, learner voices, and resource constraints. It challenges assumptions that digital music education requires expensive equipment or high-bandwidth internet, showing that even modest technology smartphones, basic keyboards, offline software can support meaningful learning when coupled with pedagogical expertise.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that electronic music devices can support competence-based music education in Uganda's Lower Secondary schools by enhancing teacher capacity and producing measurable learner outcomes. Teachers gained confidence, expanded pedagogical repertoires, and improved assessment practices through access to MIDI keyboards, recording software, notation apps, and smartphones. Learners developed rhythm accuracy (improving from 68% to 22% error rate), ensemble coordination, compositional creativity, collaboration skills, and metacognitive awareness. These outcomes were achieved despite significant resource constraints unreliable electricity, limited devices, large classes, minimal internet access through teachers' adaptive expertise and learners' communal approaches to technology use.

The findings have three key implications. First, technology integration must be pedagogically grounded, not merely device provision. Professional development should address both CBC pedagogy and technology skills, fostering teachers' adaptive capacity through sustained, practice-based learning. Second, learner voices and outcomes must be central to evaluating CBC effectiveness. This study's focus on learner perspectives revealed insights invisible in teacher-only research, demonstrating that Ugandan learners can achieve sophisticated competencies when provided with appropriate tools, pedagogical support, and agency. Third, systemic support

infrastructure, devices, training, curriculum time is essential for sustainable technology integration. Devices alone cannot overcome structural inequities; comprehensive ecosystem development is required.

As African nations continue to implement competence-based curricula, this study offers evidence that technology when thoughtfully integrated within an enabling ecosystem can help realize CBC's promise of learner-centered, skills-oriented education that prepares young people for 21st-century demands. Future research should explore longitudinal impacts, investigate ultra-low-tech adaptations for the most under-resourced schools, and examine how technology-enhanced music education can be scaled across Uganda and East Africa.

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